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Enhancing Electrochemistry Concepts Learning Outcomes Using Mnemonics Instructional Strategy: The Moderating Role of Gender

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Abstract

This study aims to enhance electrochemistry concepts' learning outcomes (academic achievement, knowledge retention and perception shift), using mnemonics instructional strategy. The study specifically analyses the moderating role of gender in each of the variables among students of science secondary school in Kano-Nigeria. Non-equivalent pretest-posttest control group quasi-experimental design was engaged for the study. A total of 270-students of SS2, consisting 141-girls and 129-boys in the four intact classes selected served as the study sample size. The students were categorized into Experimental Group (EG) and Control Groups (CG). The EG was taught using Mnemonics Instructional Strategies while the CG was taught using the conventional lecture method. The "Electrochemistry Achievement Test (EAT)" and the "Students' Perception of Electrochemistry Questionnaires (SPEQ)" with the reliability indices of 0.99 and 0.93 respectively were the two instrument of data collection used. The statistical tools used for data analyses include; Mean, Standard deviation, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Mann Whitney u-test. The results of the study, revealed a non-statistically significant gender difference in academic achievement, knowledge retention and perception shift of students in electrochemistry concepts learning. The study recommends the use of Mnemonics devices for designing learning resources for chemistry teaching and to enhance knowledge retention, perception and academic achievement in Chemistry.

Keywords: Electrochemistry, Gender; Mnemonics Strategy; Academic Achievement; Knowledge Retention, Perception Shift.

Introduction

Chemistry encompasses a plethora of fundamental principles and concepts that possess far-reaching applications in addressing mundane challenges, thereby facilitating critical thinking, self-growth and societal development (Babalola & Umar, 2023). Electrochemistry, a pivotal concept within the realm of chemistry, leverages chemical energy to generate electrical energy, and vice versa, usually in electrolytic and voltaic cell. Electrochemistry underpins various technological applications. Notably, it plays a crucial role in the functioning of batteries including those use in robot technology and energy storage device for solar system, gas preparation, electroplating processes in jewellery manufacturing,

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corrosion prevention, and the extraction of solid minerals. The significance of electrochemistry in these contexts underscores its relevance as a transformative tool for addressing real-world challenges.

Historically, the field of electrochemistry emerged in the late 18th Century, when Luigi Galvani and Alessandro Volta invented the first electricity generating galvanic cells which gave humans the ability to control electrons (Alexandra, Beswick & Yan 2022). Since then, the field of electrochemistry has witnessed contributions from notable male figures including; Humphry Davy, Michael Faraday and John Daniell. In the 19th Century, where a female appeared, she played only a supportive role to a male figure in making contribution to electrochemistry as Julia Brainerd Hall assisted her brother 'Charles Martin Hall' in the invention of aluminium by electrolysis in the 1880s. While Charles Hall became famous for this invention, Julia's name was rather unknown (Alexandra, et al, 2022). Subsequently, throughout the 20th century, there remains a striking lack of women among the popular electrochemists. Considering the numerous career opportunities in electrochemistry, this short history of electrochemistry suggests that the moderating role of gender in a proposed teaching strategy for the concepts needs to be investigated.

Gender is an analytical concept, a psychological term and a cultural construct developed by society to differentiate between the duties, behaviour, intelligence and emotional attributes of male and female (Okorie & Ezech, 2016). Nevertheless, in this study, gender is an attribute of a student to be a male or a female. Generally, in Africa and Nigerian society to be specific, male children are groomed to be strong, endure and to provide for the family. Therefore, male students are more likely to choose among the complex career trajectories which may result in a huge economic power in order to cope with the financial needs of the family. On the other hand, girls are expected to be caring, easily forgive, gentle, and harmless. Parents nurtures their female children in their formative years to take up the role of a loving wife and caring mother to husband and children respectively. Thus, whenever a woman deviates, she may be termed irresponsible, not submissive, arrogant, disrespectful, not well trained and deficient religiously. Therefore, females are mostly exposed to less difficult task to remain beautiful, so as to attract befitting suitors.

Over the ages, gender has been acknowledged as one of the major factors influencing students' Achievement and careers choices in sciences including chemistry. For instance, a study conducted by Baran and Baran (2023), reveal a significant difference between male and female students choosing chemistry in their future careers, and the results were in favour of male students. This finding might be as a result of the teaching strategy used to teach the students. A bulk of studies have shown diverse relationships between different teaching strategies and students' gender. For instance, Ani, Obodo, Ikwueze and Festus, (2021) as well as Oladejo, Nwaboku, Okebukola and Ademola, (2021) found in their various studies that male students performed significantly better in chemistry concepts than their female peers. Conversely, Adesoji and Olatunbosun, (2015) as well as Babalola, (2021), found in their studies that, female students outperformed their male counterparts in chemistry. However, few scholars has revealed in their studies that gender has no significant influence on students' achievement in chemistry when an innovative strategy such as hands-on activity was used (Ajayi & Ogbeba, 2017). Studies on gender difference in chemistry achievement continue to yield

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inconsistence results which may be attributed to unequal exposure of male and female students to different learning instructions relevant to chemistry learning (Ajayi, et al 2017). In response to this, Legg and Cafasso (2018), suggests that Mnemonics can improve students' memory. If memory is improved, knowledge retention and academic achievement chemistry concepts may be enhanced. In other to investigate the effectiveness of mnemonics in students' academic achievement further and ensure gender parity in chemistry related career, the Dual Coding Theory was observed to comprehend possible connection between academic performance, knowledge retention and perception of electrochemistry concepts with Mnemonics.

The Allan Paivio (1969) who propounded the Dual Coding Theory (DCT), argues that the process of storing information into the learners' long-term memory is better when the teacher presents information to learners in multiple forms including verbal and visual. Hereby, since mnemonics strategy encourages the use of verbal and visual explanation of chemical contents to students, it may enhance learning outcome, perception and knowledge retention of Electrochemistry concepts.

Knowledge Retention refers to committing a body of knowledge into memory for easy recall after an extended time (Obafemi & Macauley, 2022). By implication, retention of an important chemistry topic of the electrochemistry concepts is very important not only to enhance students' academic achievement in external examinations but also for the future technological growth. This has been emphasized in the National Policy on Education (NPE) that after going through science lessons, students should be able to apply the knowledge gained technologically and to better students' lives and the society at large (FRN, 2014). But this goal is becoming difficult to achieve in Nigerian secondary schools due to excessive use of lecture method causing negative perception.

Not only perception but also knowledge retention has been affected. For instance, Afurobi, Izuagba, Obiefuna and Ifegbo (2015), blamed the lecture method for low retention among students as it does not consider teaching as an active process and learners as active participants. Neji, Ihejiamazu and Meremikwu (2016), contribute that learning is likely to be more effective for learners to gain experience, retain knowledge and enhance skills in Chemistry if engaged in the learning process as an active participant rather than passive listeners. However, this criterion could be provided for through innovative teaching strategies like mnemonics strategy.

According to Putnam (2015), Mnemonics was made notable back in the 1967 through the brilliant writings of a scholar called Gerald R. Miller. Mnemonics devices are familiar things such as images, rhymes, acronyms, note cards, short phrases, and others that learning materials can be associated with for easy recall (Babalola, 2023b). The use of mnemonics devices in the teaching process is called mnemonics instructional strategy (Agbowuro, Taiwo, Mamfa & Usman, 2016). The use of mnemonics instructional strategy in science has been given different nomenclatures. These include; Mnemonics Method (Simanjuntak, 2017), Mnemonics Technique (Adadu, Ogbiji & Agba; 2017), and Mnemonics strategy (Ntibi, & Neji, 2018; Mastropieri & Scruggs 2022). In the Mnemonics devices used in this study include; letters of alphabet, traditional names like Fatima and Emeka, Cap, funny statements, and diagrams associated with electrochemistry concepts.

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According to Shamsulbahri and Zulkipli (2021), electrochemistry has been negatively perceived as abstract concept, difficult to remember and contributing to underachievement in Chemistry. Nevertheless, when students are challenged with low knowledge retention and underperforming in chemistry concepts, they may develop negative perception towards the Chemistry (Ani, et al, 2021). Apart from this, it has been discussed earlier that history has been bias fair to the female folk in the field of electrochemistry and has always been a moderating factor to be considered while proposing innovative strategy for sciences including chemistry concepts (Oladejo, et al, 2021). Thus; this study investigated the moderating role of gender on the effectiveness of mnemonics in enhancing academic achievement, knowledge retention, and perception shift of students in electrochemistry concepts in science secondary schools of Kano.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions answered in the study;

1. Is there any difference in mean achievement scores between the male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms?
2. What is the difference in mean retention scores between the male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms?
3. Is there any difference in mean perception rating between the male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses tested at 0.05-level of significance in the study are;

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in mean achievement scores of male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in mean perception rating of male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms.

Methodology

Specifically non-equivalent pretest-posttest quasi experimental research design was used in the study. As reported by Vocht, Katikireddi, McQuire, Tilling, Hickman, and Craig (2021), quasi experimental design involves the manipulation of an independent variable without the random assignment of participant into any group. This design was considered appropriate because there was no randomization of sampled students within their intact classes (Babalola, 2023a). The study population is 4,765 students of SS2 in Science secondary schools of Kano State with an average age of 17years. This adolescent population is within Hausa-Fulani ethnic group in Nigeria.

As presented in Table1, the sample size of the study which is 270-students in the four (4) colleges selected for the study. The multistage sampling technique was used in the study. Multistage sampling is a sampling technique where researcher used more than one other sampling technique at different stages of sampling process (Babalola, 2023b).

Table 1: Number of SS2 Students Sampled from the Selected Colleges

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S/N	Colleges	SS11 Students in their Intact Classes		
		Gender	No. of Students	Groups
1	A	Girls	66	Control
4	D	Girls	75	Experimental
2	G	Boys	63	Control
3	J	Boys	66	Experimental
Total			270	

Source: Field Study (2024)

The two instruments used to collect data for this study are Electrochemistry Achievement Test (EAT) and Students Perception of Electrochemistry Questionnaires (SPEQ). The reliability of the electrochemistry achievement test was carried out through Test-Retest Method and the data was analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) of the SPSS version 20. The reliability coefficient was found to be 0.991. The reliability of Students' Perception of Electrochemistry Questionnaire was achieved through the Split-half Method. The reliability of the instrument was found to be 0.927. This indicates that the two instruments were statistically reliable for data collection. However, the data collected were analysed using mean, standard deviation, ANCOVA and Mann Whitney test of the SPSS version 20.

Presentation of Results

The data obtained were presented and analysed based on three (3) research questions and three (3) null hypotheses formulated. The data were collected and summarized in Tables.

Research Question One: What is the difference in mean achievement scores between the male and female students taught Electrochemistry Concepts using Mnemonics Strategy?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Scores in Electrochemistry Test in the Experimental Group

Groups	N	Pre-test (\bar{X})	SD ₁	Posttest(\bar{X})	SD ₂	Mean Gain	Mean Diff.
Male	66	7.68	0.88	16.72	0.24	9.04	4.25
Female	75	10.12	0.82	20.97	0.21	10.85	

The Table 1 shows that the mean achievement scores of male students in the experimental group is 16.72 with the standard deviation of 0.24 and mean gain of 9.04, while their female counterpart in the same group has a mean score of 20.97 with standard deviation of 0.21 and mean gain of 10.85. The mean difference is 4.25 in favour of the female students with the mean gain of 10.85. By comparing the standard deviation of Male students (SD =0.24) and that of female group (SD=0.21), the achievement scores of every female students taught electrochemistry concepts tends to scattered from the mean almost equally compared to their male counterparts in the same group. This may be that, the mnemonics strategy meets the students' individual differences including the learning style and cognitive needs of both male and female students.

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Null Hypothesis One (HO₁): There is no significant difference in mean academic achievement scores of male and female students taught electrochemistry concepts using mnemonics strategy in Science Colleges of Kano, Nigeria. In order to test this null hypothesis, the data was subjected to one way ANCOVA of the inferential statistics. The hypothesis was tested at 0.05-level of significance as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: ANCOVA of Significant Gender Difference in Mean Achievement Scores of Students in Experimental Group.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	13.995 ^a	1	13.995	.609	.438
Intercept	12349.491	1	12349.491	537.566	.000
Gender	13.995	1	13.995	.609	.438
Error	1263.514	55	22.973		
Total	13627.000	57			
Corrected Total	1277.509	56			

a. R Squared = .011 (Adjusted R Squared = .007)

Df= Degree of Freedom; F=F-value; Sig= P-value

Table 3, shows the ANCOVA test used to evaluate the significance of gender differences in students' mean achievement scores within the experimental group. The F-value was 0.609 which is not statistically significant at the p-value of 0.438. Since the P-Value (0.438) > 0.05, the Null hypothesis is retained. This indicates a non-significant gender difference in the mean achievement score of students taught electrochemistry concepts using the mnemonics strategy. It was concluded that Mnemonics strategy significantly increased the students' academic achievement in electrochemistry concepts regardless of students' gender.

Research Question Two: What is the difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught Electrochemistry concepts in Mnemonics strategy classrooms? To answer this research question mean and standard deviation is used as shown in Table 4.

Table 4.11: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students Scores in Electrochemistry Retention Test in the Experimental Group

Groups	N	Post-test (\bar{X})	SD ₁	Post-post-test(\bar{X})	SD ₂	Mean Gain	Mean Diff.
Male	66	7.68	0.88	15.18	0.20	7.50	2.67
Female	75	10.12	0.82	17.85	0.28	7.73	

The result presented in Table 4, shows that the male students in the experimental group had a mean retention score of 15.18 with a standard deviation of 0.20, while the mean retention score of Female is 17.85 with a standard deviation of 0.28. The mean difference is 2.67, in favour of female students. That is, the female students taught electrochemistry concepts using mnemonics strategy had greater mean retention score compared to their male counterparts. However, by comparing the standard deviation of Male students (SD =0.20) and that of female group (SD=0.28), the retention scores of female students taught electrochemistry concepts scattered from the mean almost equally with their

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male peers. This may be because mnemonics strategy enabled both male and female students to participate equally in the classroom activities.

Null Hypothesis Two (HO₂): There is no significant difference in mean retention scores of male and female students taught electrochemistry concepts in mnemonics strategy classrooms.

Table 5: ANCOVA Analysis of Significant Gender Difference in Mean Knowledge Retention Scores of Students in the Experimental Group.

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	5.602 ^a	1	5.602	.314	.577
Intercept	8131.215	1	8131.215	455.679	.000
Gender Retention	5.602	1	5.602	.314	.577
Error	1124.183	63	17.844		
Total	9261.000	65			
Corrected Total	1129.785	64			

a. R Squared = .005 (Adjusted R Squared = -.011)

Df= Degree of Freedom; F=F-value; Sig= P-value

The table 5, presents the ANCOVA test used to evaluate the significance of gender differences in students' Mean Retention Scores between Male and Female students within the experimental group. The F-value is 0.314 which is not statistically significant at p-value of 0.577. Since the p-value (0.577) > 0.05, the null hypothesis is retained. This indicates a non-significant gender difference in the mean retention scores of students taught electrochemistry concepts using the mnemonics strategy package. It was concluded that mnemonics strategy equally increased students' retention score in electrochemistry concepts across gender.

Research Question Three: What is the difference in mean perception ratings of male and female students taught electrochemistry concepts using mnemonics strategy classrooms.

This research question is answered using mean and standard deviation as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Students' Perception Ratings in Electrochemistry Concepts in the Experimental Group

Groups	N	Pre-test (\bar{X})	SD ₁	Posttest (\bar{X})	SD ₂	Mean Gain	Mean Diff.
Male	66	20.68	0.88	87.34	0.60	66.66	4.33
Female	75	20.12	0.82	91.11	0.20	70.99	

The Table 6, presents the gender difference in students' perception ratings of electrochemistry concepts among the students in experimental group. The mean perception rating of Male students is 87.34 with a standard deviation of 0.60 and the mean gain of 66.66 while that of female is 91.11 with a standard deviation of 0.20 and a mean gain of 70.99.

This means that Female students in the experimental group have a better positive perception of electrochemistry with a slight mean difference of 4.33. However, by comparing the standard deviation of Male students (SD =0.60) and that of female group (SD=0.20), the perception rating of male students taught electrochemistry concepts scattered from the mean more compared to their female

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counterparts in the same group. This may be because even though Mnemonics Strategy exposed all students to same quantity and quality of learning contents and equal participation as proposed by the Gibson's theory of direct perception in 1966, female students collaborated during classroom lessons and exercises more than their male counterparts.

Null Hypothesis Three: There is no significant difference in mean perception ratings of male and female students taught electrochemistry concepts using mnemonics strategy classrooms. This null hypothesis was subjected to Mann Whitney test as shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Mann Whitney U-test of Gender Difference in Students' Negative Perception

Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig	Decision
The distribution of Students' perception ratings in Experimental group is not the same across Gender	Independent sample Mann Whitney Test	.062	Retain the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is 0.05

The result in Table 7, shows the P-value of 0.62 while finding the significance of the gender difference. Since the p-value (0.062) > 0.05, the null hypothesis six is retained. This indicates a non-significant gender difference in the mean perception rating of students taught electrochemistry concepts using Mnemonics strategy. It can be concluded that the mnemonics strategy is effective in improving the perception of Male and female students in electrochemistry.

Discussion of Findings

This study reveals that the female students taught electrochemistry concept using mnemonics strategy performed slightly better than their male counterparts. This slight difference in favour of female students may be because, they cooperated with the teacher and participated more during the teaching process compared to their male counterpart. However, there is no statistically significant gender difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught electrochemistry concepts using the mnemonics instructional strategy package. This finding agrees with that of Ihechukwu (2019) and Okenyi and Ezema (2022), who found that gender has no significant effect on students' academic achievement under mnemonics strategy condition. It is hereby established that mnemonics strategy increased academic achievement in electrochemistry concepts equally across the students' characteristics including gender.

The findings of this study revealed that the female students taught using the mnemonics instructional strategy in their classrooms had a higher knowledge retention of electrochemistry concepts better than their male counterparts in the same group. But, there is no statistically significant gender difference in the means retention scores of students taught electrochemistry concepts using the mnemonics strategy package. However, the finding is in agreement with that of Ihechukwu (2019) which revealed that gender and ability levels were not barriers to achievement among students. The findings is also agrees with Okenyi and Ezema (2022) who found that gender has no significant effect on students achievement under mnemonics instructional strategy condition. It may hereby be summarized that

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mnemonics instructional strategy increased academic achievement in electrochemistry concepts across the students' gender.

The female students in the mnemonics Instructional strategy classrooms had better perception ratings in electrochemistry concepts than their male peers but no significant gender difference was glanced in the mean perception ratings among student in the same Mnemonics instructional strategy condition. This finding might be because both male and female students were taught the same contents and with the same teaching method. This agrees with Ajayi, et al (2017), who observed that studies on gender difference in chemistry continues to yield inconsistency results which may be attributed to unequal exposure of male and female students to different teaching strategy in chemistry classrooms.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is no statistically significant gender difference in students' academic achievement when taught electrochemistry concepts using mnemonics instructional strategy. The study further concludes that there is no statistically significant gender difference in students' knowledge retention of Electrochemistry Concepts under mnemonics strategy condition.

Recommendations

The followings are the recommendations made from the findings and conclusions of this study.

- i. Chemistry teachers should use mnemonics strategy regularly in order to improve students' academic achievement in Chemistry irrespective of gender.
- ii. Principals of science secondary schools should encourage their Chemistry teachers to use mnemonics strategy regularly in their classrooms in order to reduce the effect of gender on students' knowledge retention of electrochemistry.
- iii. Resources Developers such as instructional materials designers, online academic video producers and textbook writers should use Mnemonics while designing resources for chemistry to improve students' perception of electrochemistry concepts.

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